

D. 1.3 – A multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems

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Abstract	<p>Research and Innovation (R&I) is crucial for advancing renewable energy development and efficiency within the energy sector. However, the workforce in energy R&I remains predominantly male, influenced by two key dimensions of inequality: the gendered flow of specialized Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students and a work environment that fails to support women's participation. This report presents data and analysis from the gEneSys survey, which targeted researchers, technicians, experts, academics, and practitioners engaged in scientific and technological knowledge production for the energy sector in 25 EU countries. The survey aimed to assess job satisfaction, organizational culture, work-related quality of life, and collaboration dynamics, with a particular focus on persistent gender inequalities in the energy R&I workforce and potential strategies to address these issues from the workers' perspective. The cluster analysis highlights a pronounced precariousness among women in R&I linked to greater challenges in achieving professional advancement, formal recognition, and respect in the workplace. Furthermore, women respondents demonstrate a heightened and clearer perception of gender inequalities, emphasizing the interplay between gender, job insecurity, professional roles, and both overt and covert discrimination in the work environment.</p>

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1 INTRODUCTION

Energy sector workforce remains predominantly male-dominated (Cellini et al., 2025; gEneSys Deliverable 1.1. and 1.2). Recent research and policy reports have explored the causes along two main dimensions on inequality: the gendered inflow of specialized and trained Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) students and the work environment of the sector that is somehow not sustaining women participation (EU Commission 2024, Striebing et al. 2024)

Within the energy sector Research and Innovation (R&I) plays a key role in advancing the potential and efficiency of renewable energy, of the storage and distribution of the new electrified energy supply systems. R&I also contributes to explore citizen's behaviors and attitude toward green technologies. The success of the current energy transition relies heavily on the skills and motivation of the sector's employees working in knowledge production roles (IRENA & ILO 2024 and IRENA 2023). The involvement of women in the energy research fields, particularly in the context of sustainability has been identified as pivotal for addressing emerging futures challenges as workforce diversity correlates with better R&D performance (Kim and Hwang 2022)

However, their participation remains limited not only in energy production, but also in the development of alternative consumption and production patterns. Similarly, low participation occurs in the production of knowledge within the field where only 15.7 percent of energy scholarship authors have been identified as women (Sovacool 2014).

While there is a significant body of literature and diverse approaches to addressing the scarcity of women in STEM fields (She Figure 2021) there is a notable gap in the case of the energy sector (Clancy, J., & Feenstra 2019). The presence and participation of women in the field of energy have been studied in boards and management groups of large energy companies (Carlsson-Kanyama, I. Ripa Juliá, and U. Röhr 2010), in decision-making process in renewable energy sector (IEA, 2020; IRENA, 2022) or in energy policymaking. However, gender roles and inequalities in working environment of research energy organizations aimed at addressing the gender gap remain unexplored with very few exceptions (Sánchez-López et al. 2024).

Organizational level is crucial in science development and the lack of indicators may result from intrinsic difficulties in gender monitoring. Monitoring is usually a synonym of quantitative approaches which tends to focus on how many of each sex are found. On the other side, gender dynamics are difficult to capture without perception and other qualitative indicators which are more difficult to operationalize, and which often require setting surveys or other methods like focus groups to gather primary data (Sánchez-López, 2024).

Measuring gender at the organizational level sets some primary purposes: diagnosis and learning. Thus, contextualized monitoring through gathering secondary and primary data, both quantitative and qualitative, is crucial. It becomes essential, therefore, to go beyond "counting heads" to understand not only the number of women present in energy research organizations, but also the dynamics that hinder the development of women's careers in these areas, the distribution of tasks, management, projects, and recognition (Sánchez-López, 2024).

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This deliverable presents the data and analysis from the gEneSys survey targeting researchers, technicians, experts, academics, practitioners engaged in scientific and technological knowledge production for the energy sector. The survey was designed to gauge employees' overall job satisfaction and assess the organizational culture, work-related quality of life and collaboration dynamics. The questionnaire explored persistent gender inequalities in the energy R&I labour force and the strategies to address them from the workers' perspectives.

The survey builds upon the recent study commissioned by CINEA, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (year), to help the European Commission improve the role of women in the energy transition and has been distributed to employees or professionals working in R&I activities in any energy related field (generation, storage, management, manufacturing, servicing, or distributing) of public or private organizations including research centres/academic departments, national/local agencies, companies, and businesses.

2 DATA AND METHODS

2.1 Questionnaire creation and data collection

The questionnaire was elaborated by CNR and reviewed by gEneSys' partners. Once designed, the first draft of the questionnaire has been administered to eleven previously identified individuals in order to test the questionnaire's functioning and to collect feedback to improve its clarity. The individuals tested were selected based on different gender, countries, and type of employer (public or private). The feedback received has been used to produce a final version of the questionnaire.

The Survey on R&I Workforce in Energy Transition considered the following dimensions:

1. Sociographic characteristics of the respondents: gender, age, employer, type of employment contract, care responsibilities, career level, and educational attainment (a total of 7 questions).
2. Organizational features in which they work: energy sector, country, and company size (a total of 3 questions).
3. Psychometric scales testing an individual's level of agreement about different constructs (a total of 43 questions).

The following psychometric scales have been used:

4. Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL). Adapted from Easton and Van Laar (2018), the scale measures the perceived quality of life of employees (12 questions).
5. Perceived Subtle Gender Bias Index (PSGBI). Elaborated by Tran et al. (2019), the PSGBI measures the perceptions that an individual holds regarding subtle experiences that are related to their gender identification (21 questions).
6. Perspective for just energy transition knowledge production (PJETKP). We created this scale to grasp individuals' thoughts regarding what type of

policies need to be adopted to make the energy sector more inclusive (6 questions).

7. Workplace Diversity Climate (WDC). Adapted from Ward et al. (2022), this scale measure individual's perceptions about the diversity climate in their workplaces (4 questions).

Due to the difficulty of knowing the reference universe, namely all those researchers working on energy-related research within public and private research institutions, a combination of stakeholder mapping and snowball sampling techniques has been adopted. Based on a stakeholder mapping previously carried out by gEneSys partners, the questionnaire has been sent to each contact point identified in each public and private institution in four countries (Italy, Germany, United Kingdom and Poland).

The questionnaire was then administered through the Lime survey software. The data collection lasted from September 2024 to November 2024. A total of 484 responses were collected from different countries. Among these 14.15% of responses were partially completed and were therefore excluded from the analysis.

Due to the sampling method used (i.e. snowball sampling), the geographical distribution of respondents was fragmented and non-uniform across countries. In particular, we received a satisfactory number of answers from European Union Countries, the United Kingdom, and Norway, while receiving a limited number of answers from other countries and regions. For this reason, we decide to focus our analysis on EU countries, UK, and Norway. The selection of such subset of countries reduced the sample to 357. One observation was then eliminated because the respondent did not respond to the psychometric scales' questions. Also, we decided not to include 3 individuals identified as Non-Binary, and 11 who chose not to answer. The resulting sample, therefore, comprised 342 respondents from 21 countries.

2.1.1 Gender variable treatment

Before developing the questionnaire, we sought to move beyond the binary understanding of gender typically applied in quantitative research. To account for the non-binary gender identities respondents were given more than two options to describe their gender identities: Female, Male, Non-Binary/Other, or I prefer not to answer.

Using "Non-Binary" as an umbrella term did not result in sufficient data to enable an analysis that transcends the binary understanding of gender. Out of the 356 individuals in our sample, only 3 identified as Non-Binary, and 11 chose not to answer.

Given the very low number of non-binary responses (0.8% of the sample), we decided to conduct our analyses using a binary gender variable (Female, Male). The "Non-Binary" responses were initially recorded into the "I prefer not to answer" category, generating a new variable, Gender_2. The "I prefer not to answer" category was included in the descriptive statistics to show the distribution of the Gender_2 variable. For the calculations of averages used in the cluster analysis,

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however, we used the binary variable Gender_N, in which both "Non-Binary" and "I prefer not to answer," responses were excluded, leaving only "Female" and "Male."

As suggested by Fraser (2018), when the sample size is small and lacks sufficient statistical power to differentiate sub-groups within a third gender category, descriptive statistics should be included to acknowledge all participants, regardless of gender identity. For this reason, Annex 2 - Methodological Note on the Treatment of the Gender Variable provides a description of the "Non-Binary" and "I prefer not to answer" respondents, along with a brief comparison of these groups with the Female and Male sample used in the main analysis. This comparison includes sociodemographic and organizational variables.

2.2 Method of analysis

Once a clean dataset¹ was obtained, different types of analyses were performed. In the next paragraphs the main methodological steps employed in the present analysis are reported. For a full description of the methodology, see: Annex 1 - Methodology full description, which illustrates the full Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), and Cluster Analysis (CA) and reports the statistics used to assess them.

In the first step, descriptive statistics has been calculated to provide an overview of the respondents' profile and their characteristics.

In the second step, the aim was to explore the presence of potential patterns in the responses obtained to the psychometric scales, examining their association with the respondents' characteristics, such as gender, age, professional role, type of contract, care responsibilities, and energy sector.

To achieve this purpose, two methods were carried out. First, the variables included in each psychometric scale were reduced and transformed into meaningful and statistically relevant latent constructs using factorial techniques: Confirmatory factor analysis (henceforth CFA) and Exploratory factor analysis (henceforth EFA). Secondly, a cluster analysis (henceforth CA) was performed to detect differences in the clusters of respondents for each latent construct.

Regarding the factor synthesis methods, for the PSGBI we proceeded with a CFA, and the latent factors have been developed based on Tran et al. (2019). Since we used the full set of questions, in fact, we decided to code the latent factor as illustrated by the authors. On the contrary, for WRQoL, WDC, and PJETKP, since the first and the second have been adapted from already available scales (selecting only a few questions), and the third has been appositely created for this survey, before proceeding with the CFA we performed an EFA. As discussed by Suhr (2006), the EFA is employed to explore the underlying factor structure of the data and to identify the number of latent constructs in the variables' set.

¹ The dataset, metadata and dataset documentation have been published and made openly available on the gEneSys Zenodo Community. The dataset can be download at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534057>

The EFA and CFA allowed to reduce the number of variables by identifying a total of nine factors. Table 1 reports the factors extracted for each battery of questions and items composing it.

Table 1: List of the nine factors extracted and the items composing it

<i>Extracted factor</i>	<i>Construct's Items</i>
WRQoL_F1	WRQoL_influence_N; WRQoL_abilities_N; WRQoL_goals_N
WRQoL_F2	WRQoL_acknowledgement_N; WRQoL_skill_development_N; WRQoL_decision_involvement_N; WRQoL_career_opportunity_N; WRQoL_needs_met_N; WRQoL_safe_environment_N.
WRQoL_F3	WRQoL_working_hours_N; WRQoL_flexibility_N
<i>Discrimination_F1</i>	Discrimination_biases_N; Discrimination_verbal_prevarication_N; Discrimination_respect_N; Discrimination_ambitiousness_N; Discrimination_subordination_N Discrimination_treat_women_N; Discrimination_support_male_N Discrimination_meeting_N; Discrimination_bias_acknowledgement_N.
<i>Discrimination_F2</i>	Discrimination_feedbacks_N; Discrimination_collegial_N; Discrimination_relationship_N; Discrimination_ideas_N; Discrimination_support_people_N; Discrimination_feel_valued_N.
<i>Discrimination_F3</i>	Discrimination_mentoring_informal_N; Discrimination_mentoring_formal_N; Discrimination_mentoring_senior_N.
<i>Discrimination_F4</i>	Discrimination_attuned_N; Discrimination_support_balance_N; Discrimination_policy_equity_N.
<i>Policy_F1</i>	Policy_diversity_N; Policy_culture_N; Policy_favoring_groups_N; Policy_society_representation_N; Policy_male_domination_N; Policy_minorities_N
Organization_F1	Organization_managing_backgrounds_N; Organization_accepted_backgrounds_N; Organization_hiring_practices_N; Organization_retain_diversity_N

Table 2 reports the factors extracted for each battery of questions and the relative construct identified.

Table 2: List of the nine factors extracted and the relative construct identified

<i>Extracted factor</i>	<i>Construct</i>	<i>Construct description</i>
WRQoL_F1	<i>Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace</i>	<i>The construct reflects an individual's sense of autonomy, purpose, and ability to contribute meaningfully within their professional role. This construct captures the degree to which employees feel they have well-defined objectives, opportunities to utilize their skills effectively, and the freedom to express their opinions and influence decisions. It highlights a workplace environment that fosters personal agency, clarity of purpose, and alignment with organizational goals</i>
WRQoL_F2	<i>Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities</i>	<i>The construct refers to the extent to which employees feel supported and recognized in their professional environment. It encompasses acknowledgment for good work, encouragement for skill development, involvement in decision-making processes, access to necessary resources, and a safe working environment. Additionally, it reflects satisfaction with career growth opportunities within the organization, emphasizing a culture that fosters professional development and employee well-being.</i>

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Extracted factor	Construct	Construct description
WRQoL_F3	Work-Life balance and Flexibility	The construct captures the extent to which employees perceive that their workplace provides the necessary accommodations to harmonize professional responsibilities with personal circumstances. This construct emphasizes the role of flexible working hours and adaptable work arrangements in supporting employees' overall well-being and personal commitments, fostering a healthy balance between work and family life.
Discrimination_F1	Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality	This construct encompasses perceived instances of gender bias in communication, professional respect, acknowledgment of contributions, and support for women's challenges. It also reflects how respondents recognize and interpret differences in opportunities and treatment afforded to male and female colleagues, including subtle or overt inequities in workplace interactions and decision-making dynamics.
Discrimination_F2	Perceived Workplace Support and collegiality	This construct reflects workplace support and recognition, encompassing collegiality, appreciation, and inclusivity. It captures employees' sense of value, positive feedback on their abilities, and supportive relationships, emphasizing a collaborative and respectful work culture.
Discrimination_F3	Mentorship and Professional Guidance	The construct captures both informal and formal mentoring experiences, including one-on-one interactions and connections with senior leadership mentors, emphasizing the role of mentorship in fostering career growth and development.
Discrimination_F4	Support and Work-Life Balance	The construct reflects the perception of organizational efforts to create an equitable and inclusive workplace. It captures how well the organization recognizes and supports the unique professional needs of employees, provides resources for balancing work and family responsibilities, and upholds policies that promote fairness and equity.
Policy_F1	Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector	The construct represents the belief in and support for policies and systemic changes aimed at fostering greater diversity and inclusion within the energy sector. This construct describes the need for clear regulations, cultural shifts, government intervention, and enhanced opportunities to create an equitable and representative workforce. It captures the advocacy for dismantling existing barriers and fostering a more inclusive environment that benefits underrepresented groups and society.
Organization_F1	Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion	The construct reflects an organization's dedication to fostering an equitable and inclusive workplace. It encompasses practices and perceptions related to managing diverse backgrounds, promoting fair hiring practices, and creating an environment where individuals from various groups feel valued and accepted. This construct also highlights the role of leadership in actively demonstrating a commitment to retaining a diverse workforce through equitable actions and inclusive policies.

Source: Authors' elaboration. Annex 1 - Methodology full description (Section – Factor variables) reports the items' composition of each factor extracted.

The tests performed to assess EFA's goodness (reported in Annex 1 - Methodology full description), overall, shown good samples adequacy and inter-variable correlations, with robust KMOs and Bartlett's tests. In the different EFAs performed,

the number of factors appears well-justified by eigenvalues and parallel analysis. Also, the model fit statistics (RMSR, RMSEA, TLI) are within acceptable ranges, showing that the models capture the data structures well. With respect to the CFA, for all the models, the CFI, TLI, RMSEA, and SRMR values collectively indicate that the models fit the data well. Except for the CFA performed on the Perspective for just energy transition knowledge production (PJETKP) which scored 0.1, the RMSEA confidence interval does not exceed 0.08, which further confirms acceptable models fit. Overall, the CFA results provide strong evidence for the validity of the proposed factorial structures. Most fit indices meet or exceed accepted thresholds, confirming that the models adequately represent the data.

As anticipated above the last analytical step was the CA for each latent construct extracted with the CFA to assess the presence of different profiles among the respondents. To do so, data were firstly prepared by transforming categorical into numerical variables. Missing values within the extracted factors, due to missing values in respondents' answers, were imputed using the mean values stratified by gender to ensure accurate cluster results. To ensure compatibility with distance metrics and align with algorithms that assume normalized data (such as k-means), and to reduce the impact of outliers, data were standardized (z-score) before clustering. For each factor analysed, to determine the optimal number of clusters, the Elbow method was used. Three clusters were determined for all the factors clustered. For the cluster analysis, K-means clustering was applied to identify homogeneous groups within each factor. The k-means algorithm assigns observations to clusters based on the minimization of within-cluster variance. Separate clustering analyses were conducted for the nine factors extracted:

Silhouette scores were then calculated to evaluate the quality of clustering. The silhouette score measures how similar an observation is to its own cluster compared to other clusters, with values ranging from -1 to 1. A higher average silhouette score indicates well-defined clusters. With respect to the nine clustering processes performed, we calculated different average scores. Table 3 shows these values. For our clusters, the average Silhouette score range from 0.51 to 0.69, showing a reasonably well-defined cluster structure (Rousseeuw, 1987; Meilă, 2005).

Table 3: Average Silhouette score by clustered factor and number of clusters identified

<i>Clusterized factor</i>	<i>Number of clusters</i>	<i>Average Silhouette score</i>
WRQoL_F1	3	0.61
WRQoL_F2	3	0.55
WRQoL_F3	3	0.69
Discrimination_F1	3	0.55
Discrimination_F2	3	0.60
Discrimination_F3	3	0.59
Discrimination_F4	3	0.51
Policy_F1	3	0.56
Organization_F1	3	0.61

Source: Authors' elaboration.

Finally, cluster means for the variables of interest were computed to characterize each cluster. Key demographic and contextual variables' (e.g., gender, age, education, seniority, contract type, and research profile) averages were calculated by cluster to provide additional insights. They are presented and discussed in the results section.

3 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

3.1 Descriptive statistics

To first illustrate our sample, this section reports and describes the distributions of the original variables employed in the analysis.

3.1.1 Sociodemographic variables

The distribution of the gender (Figure 1) reveals that our sample resulted a little bit skewed toward men (55.9%) with women (40.2%) representing less than half of the respondents. Under a third category "I prefer not to answer" (3.9%), respondents did not identify themselves in the binary gender category.

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of the Variable Gender 2

Source: Authors' elaboration.

Grouping the respondents according to age cohorts (Figure 2), data show a higher concentration in the age groups 41-45 and 51-55, each comprising 16% of the sample. The lowest representation is observed in the youngest (22-25) and oldest (>70) age groups, accounting for 2.2% and 0.8%, respectively. Both the youngest and eldest workers are underrepresented, reflecting general demographic trends in the R&I sector (OECD, 2020).

Figure 2: Percentage Distribution of the Age

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The distribution of age is also in line with the career level of the employees (Figure 3), with 74.7% being seniors with at least 7 years of experience. Junior and mid-career employees are respectively 13.8% and 11.5% of the respondents.

Figure 3: Percentage distribution of the Variable Seniority

Source: Authors' elaboration.

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Figure 4 shows the research profile of respondents. Within our sample, most of respondents consisted of Researchers and Technologists (68.3%), followed by Team Managers/Supervisors (16.6%), Directors/Boarder Members (5.6%), and supportive roles in the R&I industry including Research Assistants (3.4%) and Technicians (2.5%). The pie chart on the right also shows other categories, accounting for those who selected the answer "Other" (3.6%). These include individuals in academic training, such as PhD students (1.4%), administrative personnel (0.6%), and those from the business sector (1.5%), including project managers, valorization managers, analysts, consultants, and business developers.

Figure 4: Percentage distribution of the Variable Research profile

Source: Authors' elaboration.

A question in the survey explored the work-life balance dimension asking for respondents' family-care responsibilities (Figure 5). 57.5% of respondents stated that they had care duties, while 42.7% affirmed they did not. Among those who have care responsibilities, 29.5% are responsible for children aged between 7 and 17 years, while 18% care for children under 6 years old. In addition, 12.6% care for elderly relatives. For those who do not have care responsibilities, it can be assumed that they probably have older and independent children, given also the age composition of the sample. Alternatively, they depend on external support from other relatives or caregivers to whom the responsibility of family care has been delegated.

Figure 5: Percentage distribution of the Variable Care responsibilities

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The respondent profile indicates a higher proportion of well-educated individuals (Figure 6). Consistent with the characteristics of the R&I sector, 70.2% of workers hold a doctoral degree (ISCED 8), and 23% hold a master's degree or equivalent (ISCED 7). A smaller percentage have lower educational qualifications (ISCED 3).

Figure 6: Percentage distribution of the Variable Education

Source: Authors' elaboration.

3.1.2 Employment Status

Regarding the type of employment (Figure 7), most of the respondents (92.1%) declared to work in public/private academic or research organizations including agencies and public-controlled utilities. 4.8% of respondents are employed in a

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private company or corporation. Only a small percentage (3.1%) work as self-employed professionals in academic research and companies.

Figure 7: Percentage distribution of the type of employment

Source: Authors' elaboration.

Figure 8 illustrates the type of employment contracts of the respondents. The R&I workers in our sample have a permanent position contract (75.6%). Others work under fixed-term contracts (14.9%) or temporary employment agency contracts (1.7%). Meanwhile, a small proportion (4.8%) do not have regular contracts but collaborate with apprenticeship or training schemes, such as PhD, scholarships, and internships.

Figure 8: Percentage distribution of the type of contract

Source: Authors' elaboration.

3.1.3 Organization features

To the question “In which energy sector does your research work fit in?” the answers collected are promising and reflect the efforts of the researchers in advancing sustainable energy solutions (Figure 9). 56.2% of respondents work in the Renewables sector, along with innovative specialized areas such as Energy Efficiency and Demand Response (39.6%), Hydrogen (28.4%), Energy Storage (28.9%), and Transmission and Distribution technologies (15.7%). There is also more effort in the Energy Policy acceptance sector (19.7%), which is essential to address the green transition. Conversely, fewer respondents referred to other energy sectors such as Oil & Gas (9.8%), Nuclear (9.6%), and Coal (3.7%).

Figure 9: Percentage distribution of the Energy sector

Source: Authors' elaboration.

More generally, the results seem to suggest a researchers' shift away from fossil fuels and conventional energy sources toward more sustainable technologies. Indeed, due to the size of and sampling method of our sample, this aspect should be further analyzed, and while holding true for our sample cannot be generalized to the entire energy sector.

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Figure 10: Percentage distribution of the Renewable energy sector

Source: Authors' elaboration.

Focusing only on the answers of those who reported working in the Renewable sector, we gathered information on the specialization fields of the institutions/departments/companies in which they operate (Figure 10). Solar (68%), wind (50.5%), and energy economics, social and management (46%), namely renewable_sect_ecosocman, are the main areas of research and innovation. However, organizations are investing in as yet little-explored research fields such as bioenergy and pumps (35.5%), geothermal (32.5%), waste (29.5%), and ocean energy (18.5%), which may draw new sustainable scenarios in the future. It is interesting to note that, in the renewable energy sector, more than a third of the respondents (36%) declare working in the field of energy policies. that could facilitate the development and application of regulatory frameworks to drive the energy transition.

To summarize, our sample consists of about 60% men against 40.2% women. They are mainly Researchers or Technologists (68.3%) at the senior career level (74%), as evidenced by the age range in which they are most concentrated (41-45 years and 51-55 years) and hired on permanent contracts (75%). A further interesting aspect concerns research activities in the renewable energy sector (56.2%), where they mainly contribute to innovative applications in the solar (68%) and wind (50%) fields.

3.2 Cluster analysis

As anticipated in the methodology section, factor analyses (CFA and EFA) were performed to synthesize information into principal explanatory factors resulting from

the linear combination of scale items. This synthesis approach provides a valuable means to capture main trends without significant information loss and serves as a robust foundation for Cluster Analysis (CA) aimed at identifying groups of respondents with similar characteristics. Before delving into the results of the CA, however, it is useful to provide an overview of the respondents' composition, resulting from the re-aggregating procedures applied to socio-demographic variables, and the mean values (average of the responses to each item of the psychometric scales used in the survey (Table 4).

Table 4: Average's average of the responses composing the extracted factors and construct

Extracted factor	Construct	Average	Response range
WRQoL_F1	Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace	4.14	5 = Agree strongly 4= Agree 3= Neither disagree, nor agree 2= Disagree 1= Disagree Strongly
WRQoL_F2	Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities	3.64	
WRQoL_F3	Work-Life Balance and Flexibility	4.17	
Discrimination_F1	Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality	2.58	
Discrimination_F2	Perceived Workplace Support and collegiality	3.77	
Discrimination_F3	Mentorship and Professional Guidance	2.91	
Discrimination_F4	Support and Work-Life Balance	2.91	
Policy_F1	Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector	3.72	
Organization_F1	Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion	3.61	

Source: Authors' elaboration.

For Empowerment and Clarity of Goals in the Workplace (WQRoL_F1), a mean value of 4.14 was recorded, indicating some level of satisfaction among respondents with their job goals, the opportunity to apply their skills, and feel free to voice opinions in the workplace. This factor reflects a kind of self-assessment concerning soft and hard skills, for which respondents consider themselves fully satisfied. Similarly, Work-Life Balance and Flexibility (WQRoL_F3) received a slightly higher average score of 4.17, suggesting that respondents generally consider that they have sufficient flexibility to fit their work activities around personal circumstances and family responsibilities. This factor highlights a favorable attitude among employers to provide flexibility tools to support employees' needs.

However, Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities (WQRoL_F2) scored somewhat lower than the other factors, with a mean value of 3.64. This factor includes items related to receiving acknowledgment from colleagues for achieving goals, limited opportunities for skill improvement, and the feeling of being part of a workplace that does not sustain opportunity and career progression. The lower score appears to highlight issues related to workplace performance, possibly influenced by competitive dynamics, as well as a lack of professional growth opportunities.

The values for Discrimination factors (Discrimination_F1) tend to distribute around a mean score of 3, indicating no clear position towards agreement or disagreement on the existence of discriminatory situations and/or practices in the work environment with colleagues and at the organizational level. This result may also

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reflect a polarization in participants' responses. Focusing on each factor and its items, we aim to detect some general observations.

The Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality (Discrimination_F1) recorded 2.58 average scores. From this result, closer to a position of disagreement, it seems that respondents have not directly or indirectly experienced unfair treatment, or discriminatory practices against women in their workplaces. However, this result may reflect a reticence in admitting such situations outright, leading respondents to rank intermediate values, perhaps to avoid expressing more marked positions (Edwards, Smith, 2014)

The Perceived Workplace Support and Collegiality (Discrimination_F2) recorded a higher average value of 3.77. Respondents' agreement with this factor reflects positive and supportive relationships with colleagues, characterized by the exchanges of feedback, open discussion, and idea sharing. It also indicates a workplace climate where employees feel valued and appreciated.

Both Mentorship and Professional Guidance (Discrimination_F3) and Support and Work-Life Balance (Discrimination_F4) obtained the same evaluation, equal to 2.91. This value represents an intermediate stance, leaning slightly towards disagreement. For Discrimination_F3, the factor explores the availability of both formal and informal mentoring from colleagues and senior mentors in the daily job tasks. The neutral evaluation may reflect a twofold situation: either such support is not sought because the respondents are experienced professionals in R&I sectors, or it highlights an actual lack of institutional or organizational capacity to provide effective mentorship.

For Discrimination_F4 these evaluations take on a negative connotation. Support and Work-Life Balance include items such as organizations' responsiveness to women's professional needs, support for balancing work and family demands, and equity-focused policies. This result suggests a scenario in which organizations lack implementation of the basic measures for promoting workplace inclusion, particularly for female workers whose needs may require more sensitive attention, especially concerning career progression and family care opportunities. The values recorded for Discrimination_F4 and WQRoL_F3 highlight two dimensions of work-life balance. On the one hand, the low scores associated with Discrimination_F4 reflect central-level organizations that are poorly aligned with women's needs, failing to provide sufficient support for work-life balance and neglecting to implement policies fostering equity. On the other hand, the high levels of flexibility perceived for WQRoL_F3 mainly concern the general high level of flexibility characterizing the R&I sector.

Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector (Policy_F1) reveals a strongly felt agreement, equal to 3.72, towards policy measures to encourage diversity in R&I, particularly for underrepresented social groups. Furthermore, there is a positive outlook regarding the potential for shifting male-dominated cultures to encourage greater female participation in the R&I sector. Consistent with these results, Organization_F1 Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion obtain an average score of 3.61, indicating a general acceptance of diversity in the workplace. However, this appears to be more prevalent at the collegial level rather than being fully

integrated as a core organizational practice for the inclusion and empowerment of social groups with diverse backgrounds.

These results outline a comprehensive overview, highlighting both positive aspects and areas for improvement in the working contexts analysed. In this regard, CA provides an advanced analytical insight into the evaluations on 9 latent constructs, obtained as a linear combination of the variables/items of each psychometric scale. Moreover, it allows for gathering nuances in the opinions voiced by the clusters of respondents, integrating the interpretative scenario with relevant socio-demographic variables.

3.2.1 Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Clusters

CA identified three distinct clusters of respondents on the WQRoL_F1 - Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace (Table 5), who do not feel fully satisfied in their workplace in terms of a clear vision of objectives, the opportunity to make full use of their abilities, the freedom to voice opinions as well as the ability to influence decisions. Cluster 1 (-1.955) and Cluster 3 (-0.196) are unbalanced towards higher levels of disagreement; only Cluster 2 includes respondents who express positive ratings for Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace. Including socio-demographic variables to support the reading, it emerges that both Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 have a significant proportion of women: 50% and 42% respectively, compared to 38% for Cluster 3. This finding suggests that women, more than men, tend to experience difficulties in the workplace that do not adequately value their contributions. In such contexts, their potential often remains marginal and unexpressed, as does their ability to voice certain opinions. Furthermore, when considering the Energy Sector variable, we observe that the proportion of individuals working in the renewable energy sector is lowest in Cluster 1, representing only 39% of respondents. This suggests that traditional energy research sectors are characterized by dynamics less inclined to value individual skills and expression, perpetuating more conservative practices.

Table 5: Average characteristics by cluster WRQoL_F1 - Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace identified

Empowerment and Goal Clarity in the Workplace identified		Demographic		Care responsibility				Energy sector
Cluster	WRQoL_F1	Gender_N	Age	Child_6 <	Child 7_17	Elderly	None	Renewable
1	-1.955	0.500	46.132	0.105	0.237	0.105	0.553	0.395
2	0.752	0.388	47.363	0.192	0.281	0.123	0.432	0.575
3	-0.196	0.425	46.465	0.186	0.320	0.134	0.395	0.587

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The factor WQRoL_F2 - Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities (Figure 6) examines the workplace climate concerning several key aspects: the recognition and appreciation by supervisors and colleagues of work performed; opportunities to refine own skills; the support provided by employers; the level of involvement in decision-making processes; and the degree of satisfaction with opportunities for professional growth and career progression. The work

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environment is a central driver for the well-being of employees and provides added value in the research and innovation sector.

While respondents from clusters 2 and 3 express some degree of satisfaction with their working environment, those from cluster 1 show negative scores, suggesting a less satisfying and inclusive working environment. In this context, gender differences play a minor role, while the employment contract and the energy sector show a stronger impact.

Focusing on clusters 1 and 2, which reveal significant differences in the level of satisfaction and dissatisfaction concerning workplace support and professional development opportunities, some useful indications can be drawn. 50% of individuals in cluster 1 are women, with approximately 48 years, and 84% have permanent employment contracts. Half of the individuals work in the renewable energy sector. Cluster 2 includes 40% women with an average age of 45. In this cluster, 78% have a permanent contract, while 13% have a fixed-term contract. The renewable energy sector has a significant weight, involving over 60% of cases.

Two main considerations emerge from these observations. On the one hand, the renewable energy sector seems to offer an inclusive and stimulating workplace environment. On the other hand, the composition of the workforce itself plays a critical role in interpreting these dynamics. This seems to suggest that workplaces characterized by the higher presence of younger employees, even when contractual conditions are sometimes more precarious, tend to foster a welcoming, inclusive, and stimulating environment. This dynamic not only enhances job satisfaction but also contributes to making such contexts more open to change and innovation.

Table 6: Average characteristics by cluster WRQoL_F2 - Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities

Workplace Support and Professional Development Opportunities		Demographic		Employment contract		Energy sector
Cluster	WRQoL_F2	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Permanent contract	Renewable
1	-1.269	0.500	47.819	0.108	0.843	0.506
2	0.998	0.408	45.178	0.130	0.780	0.624
3	0.042	0.386	47.256	0.191	0.747	0.552

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The WRQoL_F3 - Work-Life Balance and Flexibility factor (Figure 7), includes two key aspects: the employer's availability to provide flexibility for managing work time and family care time, as well as the overall work-life balance. Organizations that show greater sensitivity to the diverse needs of employees contribute towards a healthy and more inclusive work environment. The survey data reveal that flexibility is often marginal in the research and innovation sectors, which lead researchers to intensive working hours. In clusters 2 and 3, disagreement answers on the presence of flexibility prevail, while only in cluster 1 it seems to be integrated into the working

conditions of knowledge workers. In the latter case, 34% are women, the average age is 46 years, and 52% work in the renewable energy sector. Where flexibility is allowed, an increase in care load is observed, especially for children (Child_6<: 20% and Child 7_17: 26.5%) and the elderly (16%). In contrast, in clusters 2 and 3, where workers do not benefit from greater flexibility, there is a higher share of women (38.7% and 48.5%) and a more significant care load for children aged 7-17 (24% and 33%). However, in the latter two clusters, the percentage of respondents declaring to have no caring responsibilities also increases, respectively 51% in cluster 2 and 43% in cluster 3. This could be explained by reliance on external support: in working contexts that are less inclined to grant flexibility, family responsibilities are probably more frequently delegated to partners, other relatives, or caregivers, thus reducing the direct impact on workers themselves. But it could also be explained by the fact that respondents do not have care responsibility.

Table 7: Average characteristics by cluster WRQoL_F3 - Work-Life balance and Flexibility

Work-Life balance and Flexibility		Demographic		Care responsibility				Energy sector
Cluster	WRQoL_F3	Gender_N	Age	Child_6<	Child 7_17	Elderly	None	Renewable
1	0.772	0.343	46.150	0.204	0.265	0.116	0.401	0.524
2	-2.003	0.387	46.182	0.121	0.242	0.061	0.515	0.545
3	-0.258	0.485	47.455	0.170	0.330	0.148	0.432	0.597

Source: Authors' elaboration.

3.2.2 Perceived Subtle Gender Bias Index (PSGBI) Clusters

The Discrimination_F1 - Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality factor (Table 8) examines gender-biased perceptions in the work environment, considering several aspects, including treatment differences between men and women, lack of formal recognition and professional respect for women, and limited support from male colleagues and institutions in addressing women-specific challenges. It is important to stress that the answers composing this factor were negatively worded, so only in this case, higher values correspond to higher levels of discrimination. This factor analyses how respondents perceive gender inequalities, either explicit or latent, in everyday interactions and decision-making dynamics in the workplace.

Cluster 2 consists of individuals who agree on the presence of discrimination dynamics and practices in their work environment, thus reinforcing their perception of gender inequalities (1.207). This perception is in strong contrast with the perception found in clusters 1 and 3, where respondents expressed negative scores, denying the presence of discriminatory practices. From an initial analysis, it seems that renewable energy, which is the most prominent job sector in Cluster 1 (61%) and Cluster 3 (55%).

When socio-demographic variables are included in the analysis, it can be observed that the perception of gender inequalities is higher in Cluster 2, where it is shared by 76.9% of respondents, against 32% in Cluster 3 and 21% in Cluster 1. This perception not only depends on a greater sensitivity of women to discriminatory practices, but is also rooted in the factual conditions, both in terms of employment and career progression, that women experience in the field of R&I.

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Compared with clusters 1 and 3, in cluster 2 the share of fixed-term contracts is only slightly higher (17%), and only 58% are researchers (against 75% in Cluster 1 and 69.9% in Cluster 3). Cluster 2 is also characterized by higher shares of respondents with coordination positions, such as team manager and supervisor (23%) These data, combined with the scores provided on the perception of Gender Inequalities, reveal on the one hand a greater precariousness of women in R&I, but also seem to suggest that higher-level roles do not flatten the gap. Rather, women seem to struggle more with professional progression to gain formal recognition and respect in the workplace. Ultimately, the Perception of Gender Inequalities factor highlights the existence of a link between gender, job insecurity, roles held, and explicit or latent discrimination suffered in the work environment.

Table 8: Average characteristics by cluster Discrimination_F1 - Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality

Perceptions of Gender-Based Inequality		Demographic		Employment contract	Research profile		Energy sector
Cluster	Discrimination_F1	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Researcher or Technologist	Team Manager, Supervisor	Renewable
1	-1.150	0.210	45.176	0.159	0.753	0.106	0.612
2	1.207	0.769	45.495	0.172	0.589	0.232	0.537
3	-0.096	0.329	48.284	0.141	0.699	0.159	0.551

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The factor Discrimination_F2 - Perceived Workplace Support and Collegiality (Table 9) explores the quality of relationships with colleagues, considering the exchange of ideas, support received, and in general, feeling valued and appreciated by others. The clusters represent different responses to all the items that make up the F2 factor, ranging from the perception of a work environment positively characterized by support and collegiality (cluster 3: 0.594), to responses placed in a neutral position, neither agree nor disagree (cluster 1: 0.007), to the perception of a higher level of discrimination (cluster 2: -0.727). Focusing on clusters 2 and 3 in which negative and positive values are concentrated and intersect with other variables describing the profile of the respondents, two compelling patterns emerge. The first describes collegial relationships characterized by a lack of proactivity and support, with limited opportunities for exchange, and relationships that contribute to improving the quality of the working environment. The respondents in this cluster are predominantly women (54.8%), with an average age of 47 years and the majority are researchers (75%), with a relatively low participation in the renewables sector (42%). This cluster may reflect systemic dynamics that negatively impact the working environment and suggest persistent gender differences in access to more collaborative and satisfying contexts.

In the second case, cluster 3 respondents describe a positive working environment, marked by stronger and more supportive collegial relationships. Women in this group account for 40%, the average age is 44 (lower than in the other clusters), and they have various professional profiles: 3% are research assistants, 61% are researchers, and 15% are team managers or supervisors. Also, it registers the highest proportion of respondents, 66%, working in the renewables sector. This cluster

highlights a more dynamic and collaboration-oriented work environment, potentially fostered by the presence of diverse profiles and a sector, such as renewable energy, which is more inclined toward inclusion and partnership. However, the lower proportion of women in the renewables sector detected in this survey aligns perfectly with previous research. Existing studies reveal that although the energy transition has contributed to increased national employment rates, scientific and intellectual roles within its sub-sectors remain predominantly male-dominated. Conversely, women are often confined to administrative and accounting positions, reflecting persistent gender disparities within the field (García-Baños et al., 2023). These findings underline the need to reflect on strategies to expand opportunities and promote greater inclusion of female researchers in the field.

Table 9: Average characteristics by cluster Discrimination_F2 - Perceived Workplace Support and collegiality

Perceived Workplace Support and collegiality		Demographic		Employment contract		Research profile				Energy sector
Cluster	Discrimination_F2	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Permanent contract	Director / Board member	Research assistant	Researcher or Technologist	Team Manager, Supervisor	Renewable
1	0.007	0.372	47.815	0.163	0.798	0.048	0.042	0.688	0.185	0.571
2	-0.727	0.548	47.289	0.145	0.789	0.053	0.013	0.750	0.132	0.421
3	0.594	0.404	44.275	0.143	0.736	0.077	0.033	0.615	0.154	0.659
1	0.007	0.372	47.815	0.163	0.798	0.048	0.042	0.688	0.185	0.571

Source: Authors' elaboration.

The Discrimination_F3 - Mentorship and Professional Guidance factor (Table 10) both formal and informal forms of mentoring, provided either by colleagues or by mentors in senior leadership positions. In the R&I sector, these practices are particularly relevant for entry-level professionals and those in less structured career paths within academic or professional contexts. The data reveals different dynamics among the three clusters analyzed. Respondents in clusters 2 and 3 predominantly gave negative or neutral scores, which is unsurprising given their profiles. These Clusters, in fact, mainly consist of senior-level employees, with an average age of 48 years, permanent contracts (80%), and researcher profiles (about 70%). Furthermore, a small percentage of directors are present in these clusters (7% in cluster 2 and 5% in cluster 3). These findings suggest that mentoring may be perceived as less relevant for individuals who are already well-established in their careers and may not require or actively benefit from such practices.

In contrast, analyzing the profile of respondents in Cluster 1, who reported receiving the most mentoring support, further reinforces these insights. The average age of respondents in this Cluster drops to 42, and while 70% hold permanent contracts, the share of those on term contracts (17%) also rises. Job profiles include researchers (65%), and team managers, and supervisors (20%). These latter roles may necessitate more formal and informal mentoring support, especially when associated with early management experience during career progression. Another interesting finding relates to the renewables sector: 63% of respondents in cluster 1 work in this field, representing the highest proportion compared to the other clusters. This suggests that mentoring, both formal and informal, is particularly valued and

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sought after by professionals who are advancing in their careers or transitioning to roles with greater responsibilities. Interestingly, gender differences do not emerge as a significant factor in the evaluation of mentoring practices. This contrasts with other biographical and professional criteria. Moreover, the renewables sector may offer more favorable conditions or an organizational culture that strongly values mentorship in the R&I context.

Table 10: Average characteristics by cluster Discrimination_F3 - Mentorship and Professional Guidance

Mentorship and Professional Guidance		Demographic		Employment contract		Research profile				Energy sector
Cluster	Discrimination_F3	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Cluster	Discrimination_F3	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Cluster
1	0.805	0.402	42.537	0.170	0.702	0.032	0.042	0.653	0.200	0.632
2	0.016	0.429	48.592	0.143	0.814	0.075	0.041	0.687	0.116	0.531
3	-0.691	0.418	48.035	0.153	0.802	0.053	0.018	0.702	0.202	0.544

Source: Authors' elaboration.

Discrimination_F4 - Support and Work-Life Balance (Table 11) is a linear construction of the following items: attuned to women's vocational needs for their success, support for balancing work with care responsibilities in the domestic sphere, and institutions whose policies emphasize equity. The results show a concerning scenario in which such forms of support seem largely absent for most respondents although with significant variations between clusters (-0.091 in cluster 1; - 1.159 in cluster 2; 0.0736 in cluster 3). Within the first two clusters, Support and Work-Life Balance varies markedly in poor satisfaction. These clusters include a higher percentage of women; they are 42% and 65%, respectively, compared with 29% in cluster 3. In cluster 2, where 60% hold a researcher role and 22% - team manager or supervisor roles, the absence of institutional support becomes markedly more pronounced, including with variables describing care responsibilities, in private life, to young children (26%) and elderly people (14%). Similar cases occur among respondents in cluster 1, where care responsibilities refer to about 30% of cases to children and 16% to elderly family members.

This scenario highlights the heightened challenges faced by knowledge workers in balancing the dual demands of research work and family care responsibilities. The lack of adequate support mechanisms within organizations and institutions exacerbates these difficulties, potentially undermining both the well-being and work quality of employees, affecting women more acutely in terms of career advancement and work-life harmony. Indeed, as a result of other studies, the availability of work-life balance measures is a crucial indicator for women's career development in research while also potentially making institutions, organizations, or research centers more attractive for larger participation of women in R&I (Sánchez-López et al., 2023).

Moreover, the shortsightedness of institutions in meeting employees' needs pushes them to rely on the help of family members or caregivers, thereby perpetuating

existing inequalities. Notably, 46% of respondents in Cluster 1 and 45% in Cluster 2 report having no caregiving responsibilities, many of these individuals likely rely on external support to manage these demands.

In Cluster 3, support and work-life balance are perceived positively. However, several characteristics deserve closer examination. Women account for only 29% of this cluster, and managerial roles are relatively low, with only 16% of participants holding positions as team managers or project supervisors. Caring responsibilities are predominantly focused on children, with 22% of respondents caring for children under 6 years old and 30% caring for children between the ages of 7 and 17. In addition, 61 % of workers in this cluster are employed in the renewable energy sector, which is known for its gender-sensitive and socially inclusive practices. The positive work-life balance perceptions observed in this cluster may be attributed to the sector's inclusive environment and less pressure from leadership roles. Alternatively, these perceptions may reflect more objective structural conditions, such as a limited presence of caring responsibilities, or may result from an underrepresentation of women's perspectives within this cluster.

Table 11: Average characteristics by cluster Discrimination_F4 - Support and Work-Life Balance

Support and Work-Life Balance		Demographic		Employment contract		Research profile		Care responsibility				Energy sector
Cluster	Discrimination_F4	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Permanent contract	Researcher or Technologist	Team Manager, Supervisor	Child_6 <	Child_7_17	Elderly	None	Renewable
1	-0.091	0.419	47.851	0.170	0.782	0.708	0.143	0.162	0.299	0.162	0.461	0.545
2	-1.159	0.647	46.127	0.145	0.754	0.606	0.225	0.141	0.268	0.141	0.451	0.507
3	0.736	0.294	45.924	0.140	0.791	0.695	0.160	0.221	0.305	0.076	0.374	0.611

Source: Authors' elaboration.

3.2.3 Perspective for just energy transition knowledge production (PJETKP) Cluster

Clusters related to the factor Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector reveal a clear division in respondents' opinions based on gender (Table 12). Focusing on Clusters 2 and 3, where gender differences are most pronounced, value scores range from -1.88 (disagreement) to 0.55 (agreement). In the latter case, Cluster 3 includes a higher proportion of women (66%), who are relatively younger (average age of 45) and exhibit distinct professional and personal characteristics compared to other clusters. It is predominantly composed of researchers and technologists (66%), with a notable increase in team managers and supervisors (18%). Employment conditions within this cluster are diverse, with a relatively lower proportion of permanent contracts and a slightly higher proportion of fixed-term contracts compared to other clusters. In addition, respondents in Cluster 3 tend to have significant caregiving responsibilities, particularly for children and elderly relatives. These factors likely contribute to their strong support for inclusivity policies, as they may directly experience structural barriers that hinder equal opportunities in the workplace. Their positive evaluation of inclusivity initiatives suggests a recognition of the systemic challenges faced by women in the energy sector and a demand for organizational and policy-driven solutions to foster a more inclusive work environment.

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In contrast, respondents in Cluster 2 predominantly oppose inclusivity policies, which may be linked to their professional and personal circumstances. This group consists of a smaller proportion of women (only 12%) and is characterized by individuals in more senior leadership roles, such as directors and board members (11%), alongside researchers and technologists (67%). A substantial majority (approximately 80%) hold permanent contracts, and 67% report having no caregiving responsibilities. The combination of professional stability, seniority, and the absence of caregiving duties may lead to a perception that inclusivity policies are unnecessary or less relevant to their experiences. Furthermore, the reluctance to support such initiatives could reflect a belief that meritocratic principles alone are sufficient for career advancement, ignoring the structural barriers that others may encounter.

The interplay of gender, professional roles, and caregiving responsibilities appears to be a key determinant in shaping attitudes toward workplace inclusivity and explain the divergence in perspectives.

Moreover, it is noteworthy that 54% of Cluster 3 respondents work in the renewable energy sector, an industry often associated with progressive values. However, their strong advocacy for inclusivity suggests that, despite its advancements, the sector still falls short of being fully inclusive. This finding highlights the need for targeted interventions to bridge the gap between inclusivity policies and their actual implementation, ensuring that the energy transition is not only technologically innovative but also socially equitable.

Table 12: Average characteristics by cluster Policy_F1 - Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector

Policy Advocacy for Inclusivity in the Energy Sector		Demographic		Employment contract		Research profile				Care responsibility				Energy sector
Cluster	Policy_F1	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Permanent contract	Director / Board member	Research assistant	Researcher or Technologist	Team Manager, Supervisor	Child_6<	Child_7_17	Elderly	None	Renewable
1	-0.319	0.272	47.767	0.144	0.778	0.050	0.028	0.706	0.167	0.228	0.294	0.106	0.372	0.594
2	-1.882	0.125	50.556	0.111	0.778	0.111	0.056	0.667	0.056	0.056	0.278	0.111	0.667	0.444
3	0.554	0.614	45.266	0.158	0.728	0.057	0.038	0.658	0.177	0.139	0.297	0.152	0.462	0.538

Source: Authors' elaboration.

3.2.4 Workplace Diversity Climate (WDC) Cluster

Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion management meant as the set of practices that distinguish quality, inclusive, and diversity-conscious workplaces in the workforce, registers negative ratings in cluster 2 (-1,513). A particularly relevant finding is that 60% of the respondents in this cluster are women, who perceive their workplaces as lacking in terms of valuing, including, and accepting employees with diverse backgrounds. This result, when analysed alongside other variables, such as those of caring responsibilities, could suggest the existence of discriminatory practices, including practices that would affect women most directly. Respondents included 46% who say they have no family caring responsibilities, probably due to the limited support provided by work organizations. By contrast, only 15% of respondents care for children under 6, while 30% have care responsibilities for children between the ages of 7 and 17.

Compared to other two clusters, this group exhibits a lower proportion of women employed in the renewable energy sector (46%). In addition, there is a contractual distribution characterized by a slightly higher proportion of fixed-term contracts (16%), and a slightly lower proportion of permanent contracts (76%). These data suggests that the absence of diversity management policies not only negatively affects perceived levels of inclusion but may also limit opportunities for promotion and career advancement, with particularly penalizing effects for women and other underrepresented groups.

By contrast, the factor Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion management in Cluster 3 recorded positive ratings. Yet, women accounted for only 31% of respondents, again suggesting that less discriminatory and more inclusive practices may exist in contexts with strong male representation. Still, it is also necessary to consider the role of the sector they work in about 60% of the respondents in Cluster 3 work in the renewable energy sector.

Due to its nature, the renewables sector could foster more inclusive attitudes and the adoption of more fair hiring and treatment practices, valuing cultural diversity and promoting greater openness to workers from different backgrounds. However, the low presence of women in Cluster 3 seems to represent a contradictory aspect, suggesting that despite greater perceived inclusiveness in general, gender-related dynamics may remain an unsolved issue even in sectors deemed more progressive and innovative.

Table 13: Average characteristics by cluster Organization_F1 - Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion

Commitment to Diversity and Inclusion		Demographic		Employment contract		Research profile		Care responsibility			Energy sector
Cluster	Organization_F1	Gender_N	Age	Fixed term contract	Permanent contract	Researcher or Technologist	Team Manager, Supervisor	Child_6<	Child_7_17	None	Renewable
1	0.027	0.408	47.452	0.155	0.784	0.701	0.154	0.176	0.281	0.439	0.584
2	-1.513	0.600	46.136	0.161	0.768	0.644	0.169	0.153	0.305	0.458	0.458
3	1.066	0.311	45.408	0.145	0.776	0.658	0.197	0.211	0.329	0.368	0.579

Source: Authors' elaboration.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATION

Conclusions

The analysis of the Research and Innovation (R&I) workforce survey conducted by the gEneSys project provides valuable insights into gender dynamics within the energy sector, offering significant implications for policymakers aiming to enhance women's participation in the energy transition workforce.

The cluster analysis detailed in this report highlights a pronounced precariousness among women in R&I. This precariousness is often linked to greater challenges in achieving professional advancement, formal recognition, and respect in the workplace. Furthermore, women demonstrate a heightened and clearer perception of gender inequalities, emphasizing the interplay between gender, job insecurity, professional roles, and both overt and covert discrimination in the work environment.

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The findings suggest that respondents who perceive a positive working environment, characterized by stronger and more supportive collegial relationships, are predominantly concentrated in the renewable energy sector. This observation indicates a shift from the traditionally male-dominated fossil energy sector towards a more inclusive culture within newer renewable energy research environments. Among this group, women represent 40% of respondents, with an average age of 44, and hold various professional roles: 3% are research assistants, 61% are researchers, and 15% occupy managerial or supervisory positions.

Nevertheless, the survey's findings align with prior studies, indicating that women remain underrepresented in the renewables sector (ref. E.g. European Commission 2024). Although the energy transition has contributed to increased national employment rates, intellectual and scientific roles within its sub-sectors continue to be dominated by men. Women, by contrast, are often relegated to administrative and accounting roles, perpetuating persistent gender disparities in the field.

Another notable observation relates to mentorship practices within the renewables sector. Cluster 1 includes 63% of respondents working in this field—the highest proportion among all clusters. Mentorship, both formal and informal, is particularly valued by professionals progressing in their careers or transitioning to higher-responsibility roles. Interestingly, gender differences do not significantly influence the evaluation of mentorship, suggesting that the sector's organizational culture may prioritize mentorship in R&I contexts, fostering an environment conducive to professional growth.

However, Cluster 2 reveals critical challenges concerning diversity and inclusion. The commitment to diversity and inclusive practices, which characterize high-quality, equitable workplaces, receives notably negative ratings (-1.513). Women constitute 60% of this cluster and frequently perceive their workplaces as deficient in valuing and integrating employees from diverse backgrounds. When coupled with other variables, such as caregiving responsibilities, this finding hints at discriminatory practices disproportionately affecting women, underscoring the need for targeted interventions.

In Cluster 3, perceptions of work-life balance are notably positive. However, women represent only 29% of this group, and managerial roles are relatively limited, with just 16% of respondents serving as team managers or project supervisors. Caring responsibilities in this cluster predominantly center on childcare, with 22% of respondents looking after children under six years old and 30% caring for children aged seven to 17. Moreover, 61% of workers in this cluster are employed in the renewable energy sector. The positive work-life balance in this cluster may be attributed to a combination of the sector's inclusive environment, reduced leadership pressures, and structural factors such as lower caregiving burdens. Nonetheless, the underrepresentation of women within this cluster points to a potential exclusion of their perspectives or a persistence of gendered challenges, even in contexts perceived as progressive.

The findings underscore the renewable energy sector's potential as a driver for greater inclusivity and equity, particularly through its adoption of fair hiring practices, valuing of diversity, and promotion of supportive professional

relationships. However, persistent gender disparities and the limited representation of women in leadership and strategic roles highlight unresolved challenges. Addressing these issues will require a multi-faceted approach, including institutional reforms, targeted mentoring, and proactive diversity policies. Achieving true gender equity in R&I within the energy sector is a strategic necessity to leverage the full spectrum of talent and perspectives essential for driving sustainable innovation and energy transition.

Limitation

This study acknowledges certain limitations, primarily related to the sampling approach and the characteristics of the collected data. These challenges, while inherent to the research context, offer valuable insights for shaping future investigations in the R&I workforce.

A key limitation lies in the dissemination of the survey. Following an initial exploratory stakeholder mapping phase, the survey was shared with various organizations and public institutions, particularly universities and research centers across multiple countries. However, the sample predominantly represents public institutions, with relatively limited participation from private companies. Given the active role of private entities in energy research, this imbalance highlights an area for future studies to address. Expanding the inclusion of stakeholders from private organizations could provide a richer and more comprehensive understanding of gender dynamics within the sustainable energy sector. Furthermore, this expanded participation could enable comparative analyses of organizational contexts, such as public versus private work environments, offering deeper insights into gender-related experiences and challenges.

Enhanced engagement strategies could also foster greater awareness among stakeholders, potentially encouraging broader participation across diverse career levels. For example, increasing the representation of early-career professionals—who were underrepresented in this study—could add valuable perspectives and contribute to a more diverse dataset. While these limitations constrained variability in some variables, they underscore opportunities for future research to refine outreach and sampling techniques.

In addition to its academic objectives, the survey was designed as a reflective tool for organizations, aiming to inspire best practices for fostering inclusive, gender-sensitive, and collaborative work environments. While some stakeholders engaged with this initiative, others did not fully utilize its potential for organizational assessment and improvement. Future studies may benefit from tailored communication strategies to help stakeholders see the dual benefits of participating in such surveys: contributing to broader research while simultaneously gaining actionable insights for their internal climate.

Finally, despite the efforts in carrying out comprehensive stakeholder mapping, the need to rely on snowball sampling limited the number of observations collected. Moreover, it also gave us an unbalanced data set, with low internal variability observed for several variables. Nevertheless, collected data allowed us to draw meaningful descriptive insights into the current state of gender dynamics in the energy transition field. Future efforts could focus on achieving greater diversity in

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responses to strengthen the dataset's robustness, allowing for more nuanced and generalizable analyses of the relationships between key variables.

5 REFERENCES

- Bello, M. and F. Galindo-Rueda (2020). "The 2018 OECD International Survey of Scientific Authors", *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers*, No. 2020/04, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/18d3bf19-en>. Carlsson-Kanyama, I. Ripa Juliá, and U. Röhr, "Unequal representation of women and men in energy company boards and management groups: Are there implications for mitigation?," *Energy Policy*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 4737–4740, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2010.03.072.
- Cellini, M., Loos, S., Mirenda, C., Pisacane, L., Striebing, C., & Tagliacozzo, S. (2025). Exploring the nexus of gender and energy transitions: A systematic literature review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 119(10388), 7.
- Clancy, J., & Feenstra, M. (2019). *Women, gender equality and the energy transition in the EU*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Easton, S., & Van Laar, D. (2018). *User manual for the Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale: a measure of quality of working life*. University of Portsmouth.
- Edwards, M. L., & Smith, B. C. (2014). The effects of the neutral response option on the extremeness of participant responses. *Journal of Undergraduate Scholarship*, 6, 30.
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gareis, K., Dashja, E., Hüsing, T., Popov, P., et al., *Gender balance in the R&I field to improve the role of women in the energy transition: final report and annexes*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8283>
- García-Baños, C., Costa-Campi, M.T., Pérez, A., Zumalacárregui, A., Cabezas González, A., Yélamo, P., Fernanda Guerra, L., Beratech, I., Moisés Martín Carretero, J., Monge, C. (2023). *Employment of women in the Just Energy Transition in Spain. Summary of the analysis and opinions of expert voices*. Naturgy Foundation, Madrid.
- gEneSys project deliverables D1.1 and D1.2 available in Zenodo community at the following links: <https://zenodo.org/records/10610382> and <https://zenodo.org/records/11566948>
- IEA (2020) 'Gender diversity in energy: what we know and what we don't know', Paris: International Energy Agency.
- Imbulana Arachchi and S. Managi, "Preferences for energy sustainability: Different effects of gender on knowledge and importance," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 141, no. February, p. 110767, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2021.110767.

- IRENA (2022), Solar PV: A gender perspective, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi.
- IRENA (2023) World Energy Transitions Outlook 2023, available at: <https://www.irena.org/Digital-Report/World-Energy-Transitions-Outlook-2023#page-0>
- IRENA and ILO (2024), Renewable energy and jobs: Annual review 2024, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, and International Labour Organization, Geneva.
- European Commission, *She figures 2021 : gender in research and innovation : statistics and indicators*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/06090>
- Li, X., & Mostafavi, A. (2024). Machine Learning-based Approach for Ex-post Assessment of Community Risk and Resilience Based on Coupled Human-infrastructure Systems Performance. arXiv preprint *arXiv:2404.07966*.
- Rousseeuw, P. J. (1987). Silhouettes: a graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *Journal of computational and applied mathematics*, 20, 53-65.
- Sánchez-López, S., Poveda-Bautista, R., Corona-Sobrino, C., Otero-Hermida, P., & García-Melón, M. (2024). Tackling gender disparities in energy research: a diagnostic tool for equality in research centres. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 14(1), 51.
- Sovacool, B. K. "What are we doing here? Analyzing fifteen years of energy scholarship and proposing a social science research agenda," *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 1, pp. 1–29, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2014.02.003.J.
- Striebing, Clemens, Nathalie Voigt, Kareen Klug, and Simone Kaiser. "Striving for Gender Parity in the European Energy Sector by 2050". DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24406/publica-3027>, 2024
- Suhr, D. D. (2006). "Exploratory or confirmatory factor analysis?" *Proceedings of the Thirty-first Annual SAS Users Group International Conference*.
- Tran, N., Hayes, R. B., Ho, I. K., Crawford, S. L., Chen, J., Ockene, J. K., ... & Pbert, L. (2019). Perceived Subtle Gender Bias Index: Development and validation for use in academia. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 43(4), 509-525.
- Kim, D., & Hwang, J. (2022). Is renewable energy more favorable to diversity than conventional energy sources on R&D performance? *Science and Public Policy*, 49(4), 646-658.
- Ward, A. K., Beal, D. J., Zyphur, M. J., Zhang, H., & Bobko, P. (2022). Diversity climate, trust, and turnover intentions: A multilevel dynamic system. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 107(4), 628.

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